

A RANDOM CRITICAL CORE THEORY OF A UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE AND THE INTERPLY HYBRID EFFECT (THE SYNERGISTIC EFFECT OF COMPOSITES) *

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ABSTRACT

This paper proposes a statistical approach to the strength of a unidirectional composite and the failure behavior of interply hybrid composites. The initial failure stress (strain) of the carbon layer in three-layer (GFRP/CFRP/GFRP) or seven-layer (3GFRP/CFRP/3GFRP) and the hybrid effect are analyzed using the random enlarging statistical model proposed by the authors,^{1,2} taking the stress concentration factors and pull-out lengths of fibres into consideration. The present analysis quite agrees with the existing experimental data. Some comments on the "hybrid effect" are also shown in this paper.

INTRODUCTION

Composites can be defined as two-level materials. The "composite effects" of composite materials include the mixture effects and synergistic effects. The mixture effects in composite mechanics are embodied in the various rule-of-mixtures, but the synergistic effects are rarely investigated, such as the various "in situ properties", lamination effects, hybrid effects and filament crossover effects, etc.. Composite materials containing more than one type of fibres in a common matrix are known as hybrid composites. Manders and Bader³ obtained typical load-strain curve in their tests on a series of interply hybrids, as shown in Fig. 1. The point A' represents the failure of a single carbon fibre composite, and the point A represents the failure of the carbon fibre layer in a sandwich hybrid. The failure strain corresponding to the point A is called the initial failure strain of a hybrid. The hybrid effect is defined as the percentage change (increase) of the initial failure strain of the hybrid compared with that of an all LE (low-elongation) composite in many works. But there are also the other definitions of the hybrid effect.^{4,7} Many papers³⁻⁹ on hybrid composites have been reported. However, there are some different opinions in the theoretical explanation of the observed hybrid effects. In this paper, the primary objective of studying hybrid effect lies in bringing to light the laws governing the synergistic effect of composites.

Bunsell and Harris⁵ observed the "hybrid effect" in their tests on unidirectional laminates made from separate layers of carbon and glass fibres, and attributed this effect to residual compres-

Fig. 1

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sive thermal strains in the carbon. Manders and Bader³ and Zweben⁶ reported that the residual compressive strain in a single carbon/epoxy layer sandwiched between two layers of glass/epoxy was only about 10% of carbon/epoxy tensile failure strain. It is not however sufficient to explain the whole of the hybrid effect. Thus we must look further for an explanation of the hybrid effect.

Zweben⁶ was the first to deal with the strength of intraply hybrids and tried to explain the non-thermal part of the hybrid effect from a statistical viewpoint. Although there are many excellent viewpoints in the works of Zweben⁶, his analytical results compared with experimental data are unreasonable. In addition, there are some unclear points which were discussed by Fukuda.⁸

In this paper, a random critical core theory of a unidirectional composite on the basis of the random enlarging statistical model^{1,2} will be presented, and then the tensile failure behavior and hybrid effects of interply hybrids will be discussed. Experimental and theoretical results are compared.

A RANDOM CRITICAL CORE THEORY

Fan and Zeng¹ present the random enlarging statistical model which covers the following, as shown in Fig. 2.

It is non-self-similar. The crack line is extremely irregular and may cover a large portion of the length of specimen.

Fig. 2

First, the randomly distributed crack origins (or damage) exist in composite. Next, as the crack origins randomly increase in number and enlarge their sizes, gradually and stably (including the sequential broken fibres number r and pull-out or ineffective length δ_{r-1}), the critical cores are formed. Finally, the critical cores unstably propagate up to ultimate failure.

The calculation of failure probability of the model¹ is modified in this paper in order to improve precision.

Assume the cumulative distribution function for the failure stress of the fibre of length δ is given by Weibull distribution of the form

$$F(\sigma) = 1 - \exp(-\alpha\delta\sigma^\beta) \quad (1)$$

where α and β are Weibull parameters.

Consider, for example, a unidirectional composite (two-dimensional array) under ten-

sile load. When a fibre is broken, SC (stress concentration) will occur to continuous fibres adjacent to the broken fibre. Suppose the SCF (stress concentration factor) of adjacent fibres is K_1 and the pull-out length is δ_1 . The probability that one of the two overstressed fibres will break is $2F(K_1\sigma)[1-F(K_1\sigma)]$. Then, the third failure, ..., are also expected to be the adjacent fibre. The failure probabilities are $2F(K_2\sigma)[1-F(K_2\sigma)], \dots, 2F(K_{r-2}\sigma)[1-F(K_{r-2}\sigma)]$. Finally, the probability that at least one of the two overstressed fibres will break is $1-[1-F(K_{r-1}\sigma)]^2 = F(K_{r-1}\sigma) \cdot [2-F(K_{r-1}\sigma)]$. Therefore the probability to form a crack of r successively broken fibres is

$$P = 2^{r-2} F(\sigma) \prod_{i=1}^{r-2} F(K_i\sigma) [1-F(K_i\sigma)] F(K_{r-1}\sigma) [2-F(K_{r-1}\sigma)] \quad (2)$$

where K_r is the SCF of the $(r+1)$ th fibre after occurrence of r successively broken fibres, and $\delta_r = r t_1 \sigma / \tau_s$ (t_1 - fibre diameter, τ_s - shear strength of matrix or interface, σ - remote fibre stress) is the pull-out length¹ (let $\delta_0 = \delta_1$).

It is necessary to determine the critical number r of broken fibers which have formed a random critical core. The critical condition^{1,2} can be expressed by

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_r}{K_r^B} < \sigma \leq \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{r-1}}{K_{r-1}^B} \quad (3)$$

where $B = \beta / (\beta + 1)$, $\bar{\sigma}_r$ is the mean strength of fibre of the length δ_r , that is

$$\bar{\sigma}_r = (\text{art}_1 / \tau_s)^{-1 / (\beta + 1)} \quad (4)$$

We define the failure of composite as the event when at least one of the random critical crack cores appears in the whole specimen. Let L denote the specimen length and N denote the total number of fibres in the specimen. Then the number of the random critical crack cores is $\text{Int}[LN / r \delta_{r-1}]$. Here the symbol Int represents an integer. Hence, the failure probability of composite can be expressed by

$$G(\sigma) = 1 - (1-P)^{\text{Int}[LN / r \delta_{r-1}]} \quad (5)$$

Let $G(\sigma) = G_0$ (say $G_0 = 0.50$)¹, we obtain the failure criterion

$$1 - \{1 - 2^{r-2} F(\sigma) \prod_{i=1}^{r-2} F(K_i\sigma) [1-F(K_i\sigma)] F(K_{r-1}\sigma) [2-F(K_{r-1}\sigma)]\}^{\text{Int}[LN / r \delta_{r-1}]} = G_0 \quad (6)$$

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_r}{K_r^B} < \sigma \leq \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{r-1}}{K_{r-1}^B}$$

INTERPLY HYBRID EFFECT

The above statistical analysis can be applied to interply hybrids. The specimen considered here is a three-layer hybrid, GFRP/CFRP/GFRP, as shown in Fig. 3. Suppose the diameter of LE and HE (high elongation) fibres is the same, and $h=d$. It is natural to consider that the carbon layer in the specimen under tensile load will first fail because the ultimate failure strain of carbon fibre is smaller than that of glass fibre. When an LE fibre is broken, local SC will occur to unbroken LE and HE fibres adjacent to the broken fibre, and then the adjacent LE fibres will break prior to the HE fibres. Let K'_r represent the SCF of the $(r+1)$ th LE fibre after r LE fibres are broken successively. Ren⁹ calculated the SC of LE fibre layer in hybrids containing broken LE fibres using shear-lag model. Only are the final results given in Table 1 where $\rho = E^* A_f^* / E A_f$ is the ratio of extensional stiffnesses of the two kinds of fibres. $\rho = 1/3$ corresponds to a GFRP/CFRP/GFRP, and $\rho = 1$ represents approximately a 3GFRP/CFRP/3GFRP. Hedgepeth's results¹⁰ for a single-layered composite are also given in Table 1. It can be seen that K'_r is smaller than K_r , and the SCFs of hybrids increase more slowly with the increase of r . The pull-out length of LE fibres in hybrids is different from that of fibres in sin-

gle-layered composites because crack propagation of the LE fibre layer is constrained by two layers of HE fibre /epoxy. Assume the pull-out length of pulled out r LE fibres in hybrids is $\delta_r^*/2$. Using the limit analysis, we obtain

$$\delta_r^* = -\frac{rt_1}{(r+1)\tau_s} \sigma \quad (7)$$

Suppose both ends of the specimen have a uniform strain, as shown in Fig. 3. The share of load for the LE fibre layer is P_{hc} . We now define the initial failure of the interply hybrids as the event when at least one of the random critical crack cores appears in the LE fibre layer (which corresponds to the point A in Fig. 1). At this moment the HE component can be

Fig. 3

Table 1 Stress concentration factors

Broken fibres r	Interply hybrids K_r^I		Single-layered composite K_r (Hedgepeth's results)
	$\rho=1/3$	$\rho=1$	
1	1.176	1.154	1.333
2	1.251	1.205	1.600
3	1.290	1.225	1.829
4	1.314	1.236	2.031
5	1.330	1.242	2.216
6	1.342	1.246	2.387
7	1.351	1.249	2.546
8	1.359	1.251	2.696
9	1.364	1.253	2.838
10	1.369	1.254	2.937
11	1.372	1.255	3.102
12	1.375	1.256	3.226
24	1.392	1.261	4.453
36	1.398	1.263	5.409

still loaded effectively. Finally, we derive the initial failure criterion of an interply hybrid (in the same way as Eq. (6))

$$1 - \{1 - 2r^{-2} F(\sigma) \prod_{i=1}^{r-2} F(K_i^I \sigma) [1 - F(K_{r-1}^I \sigma)] F(K_{r-1}^I \sigma) [2 - F(K_{r-1}^I \sigma)]\}^{\text{Int}[LN/r\delta_{r-1}^*]} = G_0 \quad (8)$$

$$\frac{\bar{\sigma}_r}{K_r^B} < \sigma \leq \frac{\bar{\sigma}_{r-1}}{K_{r-1}^B}$$

where

$$F(K_i^I \sigma) = 1 - \exp[-\alpha \delta_i^* (K_i^I \sigma)^\beta], \quad \bar{\sigma}_r = \left(\frac{r}{r+1} \cdot \frac{t_1 \alpha}{\tau_s} \right)^{-1/(\beta+1)}$$

The average stress σ_{hc} of initial failure of a hybrid can be determined from Eq. (8).

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE AND DISCUSSION

The fundamental data for carbon fibre are given from 11: $\alpha=0.055$, $\beta=7$, $t_1=10\mu\text{m}$ and

$E=245\text{Gpa}$. Let $\tau_s=25\text{Mpa}$, $d=12\mu\text{m}$, $L=100\text{mm}$, $W=10\text{mm}$ (which corresponds to the size of tested specimen in 3). Thus the total number of LE fibres in a hybrid is $N=W/d=833$. Substituting these values into Eq. (8), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_{hc1} &= 2.9385 \text{ Gpa}, & r=10, & (\rho=1/3) \\ \sigma_{hc2} &= 3.1988 \text{ Gpa}, & r=11, & (\rho=1)\end{aligned}$$

The initial failure strains are $\epsilon_{hc1}=\sigma_{hc1}/E=2.9385/245=0.0120$ and $\epsilon_{hc2}=\sigma_{hc2}/E=3.1988/245=0.0131$, respectively.

On the other hand, from Eq.(6) we obtain the failure stress (in fibre) of the single-layered carbon fibre composite with the same size as the median layer in Fig. 3: $\sigma_{LE}=1.9403\text{Gpa}$, $r=4$. The failure strain is $\epsilon_{LE}=\sigma_{LE}/E=1.9403/245=0.0079$.

The hybrid effect may be calculated as

$$R_h = \frac{\epsilon_{hc} - \epsilon_{LE}}{\epsilon_{LE}} \times 100\% \quad (9)$$

where ϵ_{hc} and ϵ_{LE} denote, respectively, the initial failure strain of the hybrid and the failure strain of the single-layered LE fibre composite. Owing to the same size, the size effect can be eliminated.

The theoretical hybrid effects calculated by Eq.(9) and the experimental results³ are listed in Table 2, respectively. Our analytical results are fairly close to the experimental values.

Table 2 Comparison of experimental and theoretical hybrid effects

Hybrid types		ϵ_{LE}	ϵ_{hc}	R_h (%)
GFRP/CFRP/GFRP	Theo.	0.0079	0.0120	51.9 (+10%)
	Exp.	0.0077	0.0125	62.3
3GFRP/CFRP/3GFRP	Theo. (approximate)	0.0079	0.0131	65.8 (+10%)
	Exp.	0.0077	0.0148	92.2

In fact, the hybrid effect consists of two parts. One is the curing residual thermal strain which results in hybrid effect $R_h \approx +10\%^{3,6}$ (thermal part, the value in the brackets in Table 2). Another is the non-thermal (mechanical) part discussed in this paper. When the LE fibre layer is situated in the peculiar condition of the hybrid, it is effectively constrained by adjacent materials, and its mechanical properties are improved (in situ properties). Thus the failure strain level of the LE fibre layer in hybrids will be raised. If we add the residual thermal strain, the hybrid effect for GFRP/CFRP/GFRP should be modified to $R_h=51.9\% + 10\% = 61.9\%$. Then the agreement with the experimental result is excellent. Because the given K_r is an approximate value for 3GFRP/CFRP/3GFRP, the predicted hybrid effect is smaller than the experimental value. But, we can still observe that the smaller the ratio of LE fibres to HE fibres in hybrids is, the higher will be the hybrid effect. This behavior can be also observed from a series of tests in 3.

CONCLUSION

The above statistical failure analysis and calculation for typical laminated hybrids indicate that the hybrid effect is essentially caused by the fact that the LE fibres situated in the peculiar condition of hybrid are toughened by HE fibres. In other words, crack propagation of LE fibre layer in hybrids under tensile load is constrained by HE fibre layers, which leads to the improvement of mechanical properties of the LE fibres. It is easy to see that the local stress concentration caused by broken fibres of LE layer in hybrids decreases, so does the pull-out or ineffective length. Thus the initial failure strain of hybrids increases. When the ratio of HE fibres to LE fibres increases, the fracture sensitivity of LE layer lowers further,

and the hybrid effect increases correspondingly.

This paper deals with the initial failure of hybrids from a statistical viewpoint, taking the stress concentration factors, pull-out length of fibres, shear strength of matrix or interface and size effect into consideration, and presents a new statistical analysis for the study of interply hybrids. The present analytical results quite agree with the existing experimental data.

It is more useful and realistic to replace the chain model with the random critical core model. This model can be further applied to other cases such as the intraply hybrid effect, the strength of notched plies and other kinds of synergistic effects, etc.. When the intraply hybrid effect is studied, the idea of the bridge-crack and random sub-critical core must be introduced. The paper on this work will be published.

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